

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE VARIOUS FUNGI PRESENT IN
THE ORAL BUCCAL SMEARS OF HIV POSITIVE PATIENTS**Dr Sara Zubair¹, Dr Benish Pervaiz², Dr Sana Fatima³¹ De'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore^{2,3} Nishtar Institute of Dentistry Multan**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this study was to observe various fungi in oral smears of HIV / AIDS patients and their relationship to CD4 + lymphocyte count.

Study Design: An Observational Study.

Place and Duration: In the Department of Oral Pathology, Mayo hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2018 to March 2019.

Methods: Total 35 patients smear who were on antiretroviral therapy (ART) and twenty-five (n = 25) patients without antiretroviral therapy (ART) were included. These smears were routinely stained with H&E, Pap and the specific stains recommended for fungi, namely (PAS) Periodic Acid Schiff and (GMS) Grocott-Gomori Methenamine Silver. By flow cytometry; CD4 + lymphocyte count was determined.

Results: In 26% of patients; *Candida albicans* was found who were taking ART and in patients not taking ART therapy found in 44% of subjects. In 11.4% of subjects with ART, *Cryptococcus neoformans* was observed and in 4% of cases without ART. In 2.9% patients who were on ART, *Coccidioid immitis* was noted and in 4% of subjects without ART therapy. In 1.6% of cases who were not taking ART therapy; *Aspergillus* was observed. The average CD4 + number in which several fungi were observed was less than 300 cells / mm³ in all categories. The CD4 + lymphocyte count was quantitatively grouped as Group 1 with less than 350 cells / mm³ CD4 + lymphocyte count and Group 2 with above 350 cells / mm³ CD4 + lymphocyte count. The fungi were observed to have a strong association (p = 0.001) in Group 1 with a CD4 + count of less than 350 cells / mm³, indicating an association with immunosuppression.

Conclusion: It may be beneficial to predict the increase in the colonization of Candidal and non-Candidal fungi in the mouth by modest non-invasive approaches such as oral smears, and those subjects should receive prompt medical management to prevent their spread of fungal infections.

Keywords: *Candida*, cytology, non-*Candida*, HIV / AIDS, CD4 + lymphocyte count, fungi.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Sara Zubair,

De'Montmorency College of Dentistry, Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Sara Zubair et al., Study To Determine Various Fungi Present In The Oral Buccal Smears Of Hiv Positive Patients., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Oral fungal infections in AIDS/ HIV patients may result from Candidal and non-Candidal fungi. The *Candida albicans* causes oral candidiasis occurs mainly in AIDS/ HIV individuals and is deliberated a sign of disease progression and immunosuppression¹⁻³. CD4 + can be used to circuitously estimate a low CD4 + count in AIDS/ HIV subjects in countries with inadequate resources where the ease of determining lymphocyte count is unavailable or limited⁴⁻⁵. The utmost common Candida fungi in AIDS/ HIV individuals are *Aspergillus*, *Coccidioides immitis* and *Cryptococcus neoformans*. These fungi causes' oral lesions which are usually subclinical, but apparent as non-healing oral ulcers⁶. Previously, fungi that were not present in this candida were thought to exist only in endemic areas, but are now seen all over the world⁷⁻⁸. Special staining, ie, Methenamine Silver (GMS) from Grocott-Gomori and Schiff from

periodic acid (PAS), can be used in the identification of fungi in cytology and histopathology⁹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Department of Oral Pathology, Mayo hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2018 to March 2019. Total 35 patients smear who were on antiretroviral therapy (ART) and twenty-five (n = 25) patients without antiretroviral therapy (ART) were included These smears were routinely stained with H&E, Pap and the specific stains recommended for fungi, namely (PAS) Periodic Acid Schiff and (GMS) Grocott-Gomori Methenamine Silver. By flow cytometry; CD4 + lymphocyte count was determined.

Using SPSS 18; the data was analyzed. To find the relationship between fungi and CD4 + lymphocyte count; Chi-square tests were used.

RESULTS:

In Table 1; the results are summarized.

TABLE 1: VARIOUS FUNGI IN ART AND NON-ART GROUPS

Fungi	Art	Non-Art	Total	Mean CD4+ count
<i>Candida albicans</i>	48.5% (n=17) 25.7% (n=9)	56% (n=14) 44% (n=11)	52% (n=31) 33.3% (n=20)	249±106
<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	11.4% (n=4)	4% (n=1)	8.33% (n=5)	200±61
<i>Coccidio immitis</i>	2.9% (n=1)	4% (n=1)	3.33% (n=2)	281±53
<i>Aspergillus</i>	—	4% (n=1)	1.66% (n=1)	162±0
Mixed	8.6% (n=3)	—	5% (n=3)	224±120

Candida albicans (Fig 1) was perceived as true hyphae in the oral sears, pseudohyphae and budding yeast cells.

Fig 1: Pseudohyphae of *Candida albicans* (arrow) (PAS Stain) (400X)

Cryptococcus neoformans (Figure 2) were seen as pleomorphic yeast-like cells with narrow-based budding and thick capsule.

Fig 2: Thick round encapsulated spores of *Cryptococcus neoformans* (arrow) (PAS Stain+ GMS Stain) (400X+200X)

Fig 3: Endospores of *Coccidioides immitis* on oral squamous cells (arrow) (PAS Stain) (400X)

Coccidioides immitis (Figure 3) was observed as a spherule having numerous endospores. The dichotomous septate hyphae is the feature of *Aspergillus* (Fig 4) seen as branching at acute angles.

Fig 4: Dichotomous septate hyphae of *Aspergillus* on oral squamous cells (arrow) (GMS Stain) (400X)

The CD4 + lymphocyte count was quantitatively grouped as Group 1 with less than 350 cells / mm³ CD4 + lymphocyte count and Group 2 with above 350 cells / mm³ CD4 + lymphocyte count. According to the WHO immunological classification; this 350 cells / mm³ cut-off value was used because it was deliberated as better immunosuppression level. To determine the relation between CD4+ lymphocyte count and fungi among groups; Chi-square test was used. The fungi were observed to have a strong association ($p = 0.001$) in Group 1 with a CD4 + count of less than 350 cells / mm³, indicating an association with immunosuppression.

DISCUSSION:

Although there is much literature on clinical oral candidiasis in these patients, no studies have been reported describing fungal species found in oral squamous cells of HIV / AIDS patients. Therefore, this study results cannot be matched with other analysis¹⁰. In this study, most fungi were observed with the mean CD4 + number of <300 cells / mm³, and fungi were significantly associated with CD4 + group 1 ($p = 0.001$)¹¹. These results indicate that *Candida* and non-*Candida* fungi are associated with low CD4 + lymphocyte count and hence

immunosuppression¹². The increased colonization of *Candida albicans* and other non-candidate fungi (*Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Aspergillus*, *Coccidioides immitis*) in the oral cavity of HIV / AIDS patients is of concern that these patients cannot actively respond to these microorganisms due to Immunodeficiency¹³. *Cryptococcus neoformans* have been reported to be associated with increased immunosuppression. These fungi have been reported to reach the deepest layers of the oral mucosa and spread to the distal organs of the body through blood and cause more serious damage to the

body and the body¹⁴. Therefore, oral cavity in general health can be a source of serious spread fungal infection in such cases. Regular oral examination by oral smear to detect increased colonization of Candida and Candida fungi in HIV / AIDS patients may be beneficial for these patients and appropriate medical measures taken at an early stage may prevent patients from taking serious results¹⁵.

CONCLUSION:

Different fungal species including Cryptococcus neoformans, Candida albicans, aspergillus and Coccidioid immitis were noted in the AIDS/ HIV patients and their oral squamous cells having less than 300 cells/mm³ CD4+count mean which demonstrate association to the immunosuppression state. Determination of the increase in the Candidal and non-Candidal fungi colonization in the oral cavity through modest non-invasive techniques such as oral smears may be useful to ultimately predict immune grade, those subjects should receive prompt medical management to prevent their spread of fungal infections.

REFERENCES:

- Shah, A.S., O'Horo, J.C., Tang, S., Bryson, A.L., Wengenack, N.L. and Sampathkumar, P., 2019, August. Fungal Diagnostic Stewardship in Bronchoscopy Specimens for Immunocompetent Patients in the Intensive Care Unit. In *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. Elsevier.
- Bandara, H.M.H.N. and Samaranayake, L.P., 2019. Viral, bacterial, and fungal infections of the oral mucosa: Types, incidence, predisposing factors, diagnostic algorithms, and management. *Periodontology* 2000, 80(1), pp.148-176.
- Gunasekaran, Srilatha, Rebika Dhiman, Murugesan Vanathi, Sujatha Mohanty, Gita Satpathy, and Radhika Tandon. "Ocular surface microbial flora in patients with chronic limbal stem cell deficiency undergoing cultivated oral mucosal epithelial transplantation." *Middle East African journal of ophthalmology* 26, no. 1 (2019): 23.
- Ocansey, Bright K., George A. Pesewu, Francis S. Codjoe, Samuel Osei-Djarbeng, Patrick K. Feglo, and David W. Denning. "Estimated Burden of Serious Fungal Infections in Ghana." *Journal of Fungi* 5, no. 2 (2019): 38.
- McCurdy, Lewis, L. Joseph Wheat, Jared Block, and Kiran Gajurel. "Peripheral blood smear findings in a kidney transplant recipient with disseminated histoplasmosis and elevated Aspergillus galactomanan." *Transplant Infectious Disease* (2019): e13126.
- Xian, Jiayi, Xiaowen Huang, Qiaofei Li, Xiaoming Peng, and Xuebiao Peng. "Dermatoscopy for the rapid diagnosis of Talaromyces marneffeii infection: a case report." *BMC infectious diseases* 19, no. 1 (2019): 1-5.
- Prasad, Krishna Murari, and N. K. Bariar. "CLINICOPATHOLOGICAL SPECTRUM OF FUNGAL AND PARASITIC INFECTIONS ON FINE NEEDLE ASPIRATION CYTOLOGY: A TERTIARY CARE CENTER EXPERIENCE." *Paripex-Indian Journal Of Research* 8, no. 1 (2019).
- Shah, Snehal, Sasidhar Singaraju, Einstein T. Bertin, Medhini Singaraju, and Ashish Sharma. "Quantification of micronuclei in exfoliated cells of human immunodeficiency virus/AIDS-infected female patients." *Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology* 23, no. 2 (2019): 301.
- Damasceno, Lisandra Serra, Tania Vite-Garín, José Antonio Ramírez, Gabriela Rodríguez-Arellanes, Marcos Abreu de Almeida, Mauro de Medeiros Muniz, Jacó Ricarte Lima de Mesquita, Terezinha do Menino Jesus Silva Leitão, Maria Lucia Taylor, and Rosely Maria Zancopé-Oliveira. "Mixed infection by Histoplasma capsulatum isolates with different mating types in Brazilian AIDS-patients." *Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo* 61 (2019).
- Marczyńska-Stolarek, Magdalena, and Lidia Chomicz. "Examination of oral biofilm microbiota in patients using fixed orthodontic appliances in order to prevent risk factors for health complications." *Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine* 26, no. 2 (2019): 231-235.
- Lourens, Madeleine, Lauren Philips, Carmen C. Kleinhans, Sven O. Friedrich, Neil Martinson, Amour Venter, Lize van der Merwe, and Andreas H. Diacon. "Liquid mycobacterial culture outcomes after different sputum collection techniques before and during treatment." *Tuberculosis* 116 (2019): 17-21.
- Kotton, Camille Nelson, and Christian van Delden. "Prevention of Bacterial, Viral, Fungal, and Parasitic Infections During the Early Post-transplant Period." In *Infectious Diseases in Solid-Organ Transplant Recipients*, pp. 39-50. Springer, Cham, 2019.
- McCarter, S.J., Vijayvargiya, P., Sidana, S., Nault, A.M., Lane, C.E., Lehman, J.S., Wilson, J.W., Parikh, S.A., Nowakowski, G.S. and Al-Kali, A., 2019. A case of ibrutinib-associated aspergillosis presenting with central nervous system, myocardial, pulmonary, intramuscular, and subcutaneous abscesses. *Leukemia & Lymphoma*, 60(2), pp.559-561.
- Han, Xiu-jing, Dan-hong Su, Jian-yun Yi, Ya-wei Zou, and Yu-ling Shi. "A literature review of blood-disseminated P. marneffeii infection and a case study of this infection in an HIV-

Negative child with comorbid eosinophilia." *Mycopathologia*184, no. 1 (2019): 129-139.

15. Nishimaki, Fumihiro, Shin-ichi Yamada, Makiko Kawamoto, Akinari Sakurai, Kiyonori Hayashi, and Hiroshi Kurita. "Relationship Between the Quantity of Oral Candida and Systemic Condition/Diseases of the Host: Oral Candida Increases with Advancing Age and Anemia." *Mycopathologia*184, no. 2 (2019): 251-260.